

Comparison Accuracy of the Use Carcinoma Embryonic Antigen (CEA) and Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) Level to Predict Colorectal Carcinoma Recurrency in Abdul Moeloek Hospital Bandar Lampung

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ABSTRACT

Background: Colorectal cancer is a malignancy that originates from the colon tissue, which consists of the colon and rectum. The incidence of colorectal cancer worldwide is the third largest and is the fourth leading cause of death, accounting for 11% of all cancers in human. In general, the development of colorectal cancer is an interaction between environmental factors and genetic factors. Environmental factors are divided into modifiable factors and non-modifiable factors. The recurrence rate of colorectal cancer is still very high, so it requires a precise and accurate early detection of the recurrency.

Method: Comparing the accuracy of the Carcinoma Embryonic Antigen (CEA) tumor marker examination with Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) levels to detect colorectal cancer recurrency by using Spearman correlation analysis between two variables at Abdul Moeloek Hospital Bandar Lampung during the study period of October 2019 to September 2020.

Results: Twenty one samples are obtained, 11 samples did not experience any recurrency and the other 10 samples had colorectal cancer recurrence. The mean CEA level was 139.64 U / mL and the mean LDH level was 353.10 U / L. The relationship between CEA levels and colorectal cancer recurrence was significant with a correlation coefficient of 0.663, while the relationship between LDH levels and colorectal cancer recurrence was insignificant with a correlation coefficient of 0.213.

Conclusion: CEA is more accurate than LDH to predict the recurrency of colorectal cancer, so that in clinical practice CEA is better used to predict colorectal cancer recurrence.

KEYWORDS: CEA, Colorectal cancer recurrency, LDH

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BACKGROUND

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a malignancy that originates from the colon tissue, which consists of the colon (the longest part of the large intestine) and the rectum (the last small part of the large intestine before the anus). Based on epidemiological data according to the American Cancer Society, colorectal cancer is the third most common cancer and is the third leading cause of death in men and women in the United States.¹ The incidence of colorectal cancer worldwide ranks third and ranks fourth as a cause of death, and is 11% from all cancers in human.²

In general, CRC's development is an interaction between environmental factors and genetic factors. The

unmodifiable factors are individual and family history of CRC or adenoma polyps and individual history of chronic inflammatory bowel disease.^{3,4,5,6} Modifiable risk factors which play role in CRC are inactivity, obesity, high consumption of red meat, smoking and moderate alcohol consumption.^{6,7,8} While physical activity, a fibrous diet and intake of vitamin D are included as protective factors.

Carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) is an oncofetal antigen that increases up to 75% in cases with recurrent colorectal cancer. At a level of 10 IU / L as the cutoff point, a sensitivity of 44% and a specificity of 90% was obtained to detect CRC recurrency. CEA has often increased a

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median of 4.5 to 8 months before the onset of symptoms, so it is very useful to detect recurrency earlier.

One of the laboratory examinations to determine CRC recurrency is blood chemistry test for lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). Generally, if there's LDH levels elevation found, this can indicate any tissue damage.

METHOD

This research is a descriptive analytic study with a cross sectional approach. This design was determined because we wanted to compare the accuracy of the diagnosis of tumor markers for Carcinoma Embryonic Antigen (CEA) and Lactate Dehydrogenase Levels to predict colorectal cancer recurrency. Spearman's analysis is used to analyze the relationship between variables.

RESULTS

The characteristics of study subjects, the mean age was 45.48 years, the mean CEA level was 139.64 U / ml and the mean LDH level was 353.10 U / L. All of the 21 samples, surgery and chemotherapy were performed. The sample also has chemotherapy. In this study, 11 people (52.38%) did not experience recurrency and 10 (47.62%) experienced recurrency and metastases.

Table 1. The characteristics of study subjects

Characteristics		N	%
Surgery	Hemicolectomy	9	42.85
	AR/LAR/VLAR	6	28.57
	Abdominal-Perineal Resection	3	14.28
	Tranversectomy	1	4.76
	Sigmoidectomy	2	9.52
Chemotherapy	Folfiri – Avastin	3	14.28
	Folfox	5	23.81
	Folfox – Avastin	2	9.52
	Simplified biweekly	11	52.38
Recurrency	(-)	11	52.38
	(+)	10	47.62
CEA level	< 5 ng/ml	8	38.10
	6 - 10 ng/ml	2	9.52
	21 - 50 ng/ml	4	19.05
	> 50 ng/ml	7	33.33
LDH level	< 250	1	4.76
	Elevation < 3x	20	95.24

Table 2. CEA and LDH levels

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	21	16.00	67.00	45.48	10.00
CEA level	21	1.22	1856.00	139.64	403.86
LDH level	21	43.00	593.00	353.10	123.30

The relationship between CEA levels and recurrency of colorectal cancer in patients at Abdul Moeloek Hospital has a correlation coefficient value of 0.663 with p value of 0.001; because the value of $p = 0.001 < 0.05$ ($\alpha = 5\%$), it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between CEA levels and the recurrency of colorectal cancer. The direction of the correlation is positive, which shows that the higher CEA level, the higher the recurrence rate of colorectal cancer with a high correlation category.

The relationship between LDH levels and the recurrency of colorectal cancer in patients at Abdul Moeloek Hospital has a correlation coefficient of 0.213 with p value of 0.353; because the value of $p = 0.353 > 0.05$ ($\alpha = 5\%$), it can be concluded that there is no significant relationship between LDH levels and colorectal cancer recurrence. The direction of the positive correlation indicates that the higher the LDH level will further increase the recurrency of colorectal cancer with a low correlation category.

DISCUSSION

The relationship between CEA levels and colorectal cancer recurrency is very significant, where the correlation coefficient value from the Spearman analysis is 0.663. Meanwhile, the relationship between LDH levels and colorectal cancer recurrence is not significant, where the correlation coefficient value from the Spearman analysis is 0.213. An increase in the plasma CEA ratio is found in people with colon cancer, stomach cancer, pancreatic cancer, lung cancer, breast cancer, thyroid cancer, inflammatory colitis, pancreatitis, cirrhosis, COPD, and Crohn's disease. This is because CEA is an immunoglobulin family glycoprotein antigen with 29 genetic files that play a role in cell adhesion. CEA levels can predict recurrence of colorectal cancer, but they are not very sensitive to screening and diagnostic of colorectal cancer. LDH is widely expressed in body tissues, such as blood cells, muscle cells, bone cells, skin cells and tumor cells. Because it is released during tissue damage it can be used to predict disease and its recurrence.^{10,11}

To predict the recurrence of colorectal cancer, the results showed that using CEA levels was more effective than using LDH levels. This is because the glycoproteins produced by tumor cells can be detected earlier than the level of cell damage that occurs so that LDH levels take

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longer to be detected. LDH levels indicate the degree of a disease's seriousness or a disease's severity, rather than to see a disease's recurrence rate. Therefore, with this study, it is more sensitive to diagnose colorectal cancer recurrence using CEA levels. So that in clinical practice we only use CEA to predict disease recurrence.

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